

Advanced Systems development with Machine Learning.

Software development has over the years grown to become complex with the advancement of new processing hardware, demanding user experience, complexity of codes, innovations and demand for updates. Also, the rapid growth of developmental paradigm in software languages, and cloud computing services, software developers are faced with several challenges to deliver software that are continuous, integral and agile. Modern software applications using Machine learning (ML) is geared to transform the nature of software development in fundamental ways. We will be exploring how the integration of machine learning models has greatly advanced software development in recent times.

Development tools applying Machine Learning (ML).

Writing codes for robust applications has experienced complexity in terms of volume and speed of execution which normally involves increased demand for processing cycles and require more space in memory. For instance, in security technologies, there is a need to run through several lines of codes and test vulnerability in a short time. Today many security firms are exploring Machine learning as an integrating model to rapidly process codes while improving the precision of the test outcomes. Outcomes that present faster processing cycles and lower risk become the desired combination required to stay ahead of their game. Machine learning algorithms can help to look for vulnerabilities in software. It algorithms will sieve through the code to look for flaws and sometimes recommend features to fix them. This will enable developers working on large codebase to see the pattern and improve on their security patches.

1.The cloud and ML frameworks

The cloud has become one of the most important development tool or infrastructure that has enabled the rapid development of software applications in recent times. With several service providers such as Amazon Web services (AWS), Google Cloud Platform and Microsoft Azure, developers can easily run codes using cloud service infrastructures that can support speed and adaptability. The move to

the cloud has been one of the major factors responsible for the breakthrough in software advancement be it web or mobile. It is this scalability and accessibility of cloud applications that has helped to push continues development and software development operations including agile development to new heights. To further improve software development in the light of high performance such as faster cloud computing of applications, we require the performance and analytics of machine learning models which will support rapid testing and deployment. Machine learning is handy for deep analysis of large data and can support rapid development and deployment. ML frameworks and environments offer great code coverage such as providing statistical analysis, functionality and adequate testing throughout the entire application.

2. Machine Learning replacing code.

Today, ML is rapidly making code more efficient. Google's TensorFlow has the capability to replace a 500,000 lines of code with just 500 lines. To drive deeper in this understanding, Google's tensor flow represents a neural network that has be trained to translate. But what is more important is how this neural network can be revisited and retrained on new data as biases and prejudices are discovered and language changes and usage shifts. The cost of training a neural network of any complexity cannot be compared to debugging a codebase that is gigantic.

3. ML Infrastructure and Data management.

It is no news that machine learning has capabilities to outperform the traditional database indexes. It's prediction feature can learn where data is stored making, sorting and finding data far more dynamic as this will require less memory space and less time required to cover multidimensional indexes. This helps in dynamic database updating, query optimization, learned multidimensional indexing, retraining performances and others. ML can also be used to tune databases for performances where it can simplify many configuration settings into a simplified tuned database. In the future, managing data infrastructure will move beyond setting hundreds of configurations parameters to training the system to fine-tune its workload performance. With software such as MLFlow, managing and

monitoring large data infrastructures is done effortlessly through deep learning for precise detection or prevention of outage.

4. How ML is improving Data science

The rise of deep learning, has exploded the knowledge and science of data. Data can now be seen in different light with transformational insights. Data scientist can now use tools such as the Automatic statisticians that explores data analysis and provide statistical models for high-dimensional series with better precision than ever. It is also possible to automate learning models today. The process of automating machine learning can provide cloud-based tools required to sequence the creation of machine learning models as seen in Google's AutoML and Amazon Sagemaker. Model creation and management requires consistent monitoring and tuning, new algorithms such as bandit uses reinforced learning for A/B testing.

5. Machine Learning in creative Game development.

Today, Game developers are actively exploring machine learning models that can be used to develop different backgrounds and scenes which will evoke reality. Against the traditional methods of drawing and image creation which require so much time and expertise of professional, machine learning models can be used to model the behavior of a non-player character (NPC). Since NPC's can learn behavior, creativity in game play can be further enriched as against the traditional explicit programming of a NPC.

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